

Role of deformation and fluids in the evolution of the anorthosites from Krossøy in the Bergen Arcs, Norway

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The Bergen Arcs, in Norway, consist of several arcuate nappes formed during the Caledonian orogeny 440-420 Ma ago [1,2] when the western margin of Baltica was subducted below Laurentia. This Caledonian orogeny overprinted many of the anorthosites that formed the 930 Ma old [1] granulitic basement. This overprint resulted in both amphibolites and eclogites and have been observed in shear zones within the rocks of the well-studied island of Holsnøy, located on the western margin of the Lindås Nappe. On the adjacent island of Radøy, the Caledonian overprint is associated with amphibolite facies shear zones [3,4].

In the northern margin of the Bergen Arcs, near the Bergen Arcs Shear Zone, the much less-studied island of Krossøy also exposes the anorthosites from the old granulitic basement and here the Caledonian overprint also resulted only in amphibolite facies metamorphism. The anorthosites in Krossøy are intruded by a series of subparallel mafic granulitic dykes forming the Krossøy dyke swarm, that has never previously been described elsewhere in the Bergen Arcs. The style of deformation in the granulites and the textural evolution in the amphibolite facies overprint are also markedly different from the rocks on Holsnøy and Radøy. The development of ductile Caledonian shear zones may have been facilitated by initial brittle failure of the basement accompanied by fluid infiltration [5]. Here we investigate the influence of this deformation and fluid infiltration on different features observed on these rocks such as: the occurrence of plagioclase coronas around the garnets on the dykes; the presence of different types of symplectites; the variability of size, deformation and composition observed on the anorthositic feldspars; or the local changes of fluid composition along cm- long fractures. We will show our first analytical results on some of these key features and discuss their relevance in the context of the previous studies of the Bergen Arcs.

References:

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